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Научная статья

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ СРЕДСТВА МАЛОФОРМАТНЫХ ТЕКСТОВ В АНГЛОЯЗЫЧНОЙ РЕКЛАМЕ МОДНОЙ ОДЕЖДЫ

LINGUISTIC MEANS OF SMALL-FORMAT TEXTS IN ENGLISH FASHION ADVERTISING

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Данная статья посвящена изучению малоформатных текстов и их лингвистических особенностей в современной англоязычной рекламе одежды модных брендов. В работе выявлены и проанализированы наиболее характерные лингвистические особенности малоформатных текстов. Согласно результатам исследования, создание идентичности бренда и эмоциональное воздействие в контексте семиотики являются основными элементами, формирующими лингвистическую уникальность малоформатных текстов в рекламе модной одежды. Так, выявленные особенности данных рекламных текстов помогают представлять коммерческое сообщение в качестве эстетического высказывания, которое делает продукт более привлекательным для потребителя.

This article examines short texts and their linguistic characteristics in contemporary English-language fashion advertising. The study identifies and analyzes the most characteristic linguistic features of short texts. According to the study's findings, the creation of brand identity and emotional impact within a semiotic context are key elements that shape the linguistic uniqueness of short texts in fashion advertising. The identified characteristics of these advertising texts help present the commercial message as an aesthetic statement, making the product more appealing to consumers.

Ключевые слова: *малоформатный текст, английский язык, реклама в сфере моды, лингвистические особенности, рекламное сообщение.*

Key words: *small-format text, English language, fashion advertising, linguistic features, advertising message.*

Advertising is the main communication tool that different companies use to build emotional associations and positive perceptions of the brand. The research investigates one of the forms of advertising messages — small-format texts — that are widely used to attract customers' attention. The relevance of the research is determined by the creation new ways of advertising products that impact a mass audience. Thus, new linguistic phenomena arouse the interest of linguists in this sphere.

The problem of this study is to identify systemic linguistic mechanisms in fashion advertising. Despite the prevalence of such texts, it is still unclear by what specific linguistic means it is possible to maintain semantic and value saturation, structural coherence and emotionality.

The work was performed on the material of one hundred advertisements of luxury, premium, and mass-market online shops of such brands as Prada, Miu Miu, Alaïa, Balmain, Zara, PULL&BEAR.

During the study, such a method as stylistic analysis was used in order to identify expressive means employed in fashion advertising mini-texts.

The theoretical basis of the presented research was made up of scientific works of Russian and foreign linguists in the field of linguistics (Cherkunova M. V., Kharkovskaya A. A., Kubryakova E. S., Park C. W., Macinnis D. J., Starostina Iu. S.).

The results revealed some features that are typical for such kind of English texts: the size of a text, visual integrativity, the use of various linguistic means, fashion terms, and borrowed lexis.

Park, MacInnis, and Priester (2010) state that brand attachment develops when customers have a personal and emotional connection to the brand, which can be formed with the help of regular and pertinent advertising messages [8, p. 4].

Nowadays, advertisers face a challenge to create a message that can grab people's attention as we live in the world where we get all the information very quickly and analyze it at the same pace. According to this tendency to optimize communication, short texts that require less time for reading and evaluating are more preferable, especially considering advertising texts [1, c. 325].

Short texts, also known as small-format or mini-format texts, are more common than ever, and their quantitative representation and qualitative variability in different communicative situations are higher than ever [5, c. 249].

E. S. Kubryakova notes that "small-format texts" are recognized as the focus of "the most representative features of the [text] category in a correlated form, i.e. acting as a bundle of features correlated with each other" [2, c. 74].

When it comes to small-format texts, the issue of their size is especially urgent. Numerous studies indicate that one utterance – which can even be conveyed in a single word – is the minimum barrier for such messages. The upper limit is not clearly determined, but the approximate size of such texts can contain up to 600 lexical units [7, P. 63]. There is an example of small-format texts in advertising of Prada bag that contains forty lexical units:

The iconic Prada Galleria bag is a timeless masterpiece of elegance and class. Crafted in luxurious Saffiano leather, it seamlessly blends industrial precision with exceptional craftsmanship. This essential model exudes sophistication, making it the perfect accessory for refined and stylish occasions. (*Retrieved from <https://www.prada.com/ww/en.html>*).

Another small-format text includes just three words:

Creations for unique moments (*Retrieved from <https://www.miumiu.com/ww/en>*).

In addition, the fact that a text should be short implies a special concentration of information contained in the advertising text — its high semantic density — and determines the structure of the text [3, c. 658].

A small-format text should be visually uniform. All components must work together to create a structure, contain content, and be consistent. This forms one of the features of small-format texts — visual integrativity [6, c. 53].

The Winter Spring 26 campaign acts as a 360-degree study of the Alaïa silhouette. Garments are revealed in motion, from every angle, intimately. (Retrieved from <https://www.maison-alaia.com/en-fr/>).

This text has the structure that helps to see the campaign as a dynamic and full-of-energy show, allowing to see every detail of new masterpieces.

Small-format advertising media texts are characterized by "emotionality" of speech, "creativity", the use of various linguistic means and literary devices, such as vivid metaphors, epithets, evaluative qualities at the lexical and grammatical level to describe clothing in the best and most interesting way in order to attract customers' attention.

Casual ease meets festive elegance, with vintage touches and artisanal craftsmanship creating sophisticated, unexpected looks. (Retrieved from <https://www.miumiu.com/ww/en>).

The example includes a plenty of descriptives, such as '*festive elegance*', '*vintage touches*' '*artisanal craftsmanship*', '*sophisticated*', '*unexpected*', making an image of something luxurious and cutting-edge. Moreover, the advertisers used personification to concretize abstract advantages of clothing items and create a narration of the product. This simplifies the processing of information and incorporates the brand into the consumer's personal history.

At the heart of this ritual is the Prada Galleria: a talisman, an amulet, a vessel of change. Each ingredient is more than matter – it is symbol: time, memory, nature, the voice of animals, art, sacrifice. Like its protagonist, the Prada Galleria transforms season after season, while remaining eternal. (Retrieved from <https://www.prada.com/ww/en.html>).

The most evident linguistic tool in this example is metaphor. The advertisers compare a bag with '*a talisman, an amulet, a vessel of change*', and its elements with '*time, memory, nature, the voice of animals, art, sacrifice*'.

As these are small-format texts in the advertising discourse, one of the typical features is the usage of fashion terms meaning different products, tailoring, and design.

Accessories turn into attire and utility into a decoration in the Prada Re-Nylon women's collection, featuring hybrid designs that blend sportswear elements with luxury silhouettes and approaches. Full-skirted and slender cocktail dresses paired with cocoon-coats define the selection, completed by iconic footwear and accessories like the Prada nylon backpack. (Retrieved from <https://www.prada.com/ww/en.html>).

There are some examples of specific fashion terms that were used in the advertisement of a new Prada women's collection: *full-skirted, cocktail dresses, cocoon-coats, nylon*.

There is a propensity to use borrowed lexis in English advertising small-format texts, especially borrowings from French and Italian, since France and Italy are considered to be centers of fashion and design.

First conceived in 2007, the Prada Galleria has become an icon of the Prada universe, named after the historic boutique opened by Mario Prada in Milan's Galleria Vittorio Emanuele II in 1913. A symbol of constant reinvention, it mirrors the times while remaining timeless. (Retrieved from <https://www.prada.com/ww/en.html>).

The example above contains the names of a product *Prada Galleria*, a designer *Mario Prada*, and a place *Galleria Vittorio Emanuele II* in Italian, as well as a word *boutique* borrowed from French and commonly used.

Special attention should be paid to the expressive syntax of small-format advertising texts in English. The expressive syntax is presented in the form of imperative mood constructions, as well as interrogative constructions in combination with an ellipsis. The imperative mood additionally motivates a person to pay attention to a product and make a purchase, while the second option creates an illusion of dialogue and develops a relationship with the customer [4, c. 495].

For example:

Dive into the trendiest world of fashion and find here the latest trends for men and women. (Retrieved from <https://www.pullandbear.com/us/>).

The clothing brand 'PULL&BEAR' is using an imperative mood to draw people's attention.
Conclusion.

Summing up all of the above and analyzing the studied material, it is worth noting that the number of small-format texts in English-language advertising is increasing every day, and the texts themselves are only getting shorter. At the same time, they retain their coherence, emotionality, and structure, and combine such features as the size of a text, visual integrativity, metaphors, epithets, evaluative qualities, descriptives, fashion terms, borrowed lexis, imperative mood, and interrogative constructions in syntax. All of them allow fashion brands to successfully promote and sell their products and develop in the market. Small-format texts in fashion advertising are an excellent tool for the succinct transmission of brand values and direct appeal to emotions, working at the intersection of linguistics, semiotics, and psychology of perception.

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